

THE IMPORTANCE OF GROUP WORK AND PAIR WORK FOR IMPROVING LISTENING SKILL

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Annotation. This article is written with an aim of exploring the significant role listening skill plays in language acquisition. In addition, there is provided enough information about how to organize a listening lessons, with what activities, games as a teaching method of these days. Therefore this article is beneficial for both educators and learners to form a plan for developing listening skill in a quick manner.

Key words: listening comprehension, audios, games, authentic materials, modern teaching methods.

Аннотация. Эта статья написана с целью изучения важной роли навыка аудирования в освоении языка. Кроме того, в ней предоставлено достаточно информации о том, как организовать уроки аудирования, с какими видами деятельности, играми как методом обучения в наши дни. Поэтому эта статья полезна как для педагогов, так и для учащихся, чтобы быстро составить план развития навыка аудирования.

Ключевые слова: аудирование, аудио, игры, аутентичные материалы, современные методы обучения.

INTRODUCTION

Listening is one of the four language skills which are required for language acquisition. In linguistics, we have four language skills, two (listening and reading) are receptive skills in which learners are inclined to absorb information from audial input and written works, another two (writing and speaking) are considered to be productive skills which demand production of oral and written answers. Among these, listening skill is of great significance as most of our time is spent on listening to others consciously and unconsciously, such as, lectures, explanation of a lesson in educational settings, discussions, debates, chats among friends and casual acquaintants, noise of transportation, birds chirping outside the street and others.

As for the lesson process of teaching listening, it is organized in three parts based on modern language teaching methods. Those are pre-listening, while-listening and post listening activities which have a special aim during the lesson. When it comes to the first stage of listening practise with pre-listening tasks, they are specialized for preparing students for an upcoming important one. That crucial one is accepted as while-listening which requires the use of authentic materials to make the learning process more engaging and straightforward. Lastly, after finishing the task, learners are given extra listening task called post-listening to analyze and evaluate their understandings.

In addition to all given above, in modern teaching methods - communicative language teaching (CLT) - there are more active ways of teaching listening, such as, through pair and group works. The reason for that students can feel more comfort with someone from the class, it means peers, rather than their teachers, because for their classmates it is highly possible to make a mistake, but vice versa is true for the teachers. Furthermore, there exist several beneficial sides of pair and group works:

- developing communication and listening skills;
- improving critical thinking and problem solving abilities;
- increasing enthusiasm for language learning;
- active participation in a classroom discussions.

Teachers have been applying different pair and group works for an active listening practise since they turned to modern teaching methods (MTM) including:

1. Draw This

A full-group activity where students follow simple drawing instructions while listening cooperatively. They listen to an audio explaining people, animals, nature, place or situation, and students have to describe it on the paper by drawing based on audio explanation. The reason why they must be attentive is that, the color, shape, appearance all are crucially vital to be true with the one spoken in the audio.

2. Train of Thoughts

An active listening exercise that helps students maintain attention and connect ideas logically. This activity requires being attentive while listening, because to understand the meaning they have to listen attentively, as a group after listening, they must explain each sentence they listened to to their teacher one by one.

3. Non-verbal communication signals

A small group game that helps participants become more aware of non-verbal cues speakers use.

Besides this, instructors can integrate other types of pair and group works into their classrooms. For example, Think-pair-share, Learning by teaching, Peer tutoring, Jigsaws, Pair or group discussions, Completing shared tasks, Activities or games with a competitive element, Drama and role play, Information exchange activities. All of these are in some parts help to boost and practise listening skill.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, currently, listening is a kind of skill which can be developed by the help of different strategies and activities mentioned above. Especially, pair and group works are of great significance to boost listening skill, since they aid to create more interactive and intriguing lesson environment for teachers and students. Why is this so? The reason for that, evidently, school pupils have a short attention span, it means that they cannot listen to a teacher more than 15-20minutes. Admittedly, in such cases, games must be applied through organizing pairs and groups to help learners have fun and relaxation during the lesson. Therefore, gamification has been used around the globe in communicative language teaching (CLT). It seems that it is more fun to learn by gaming, working as a team, this, in turn, fosters their relationships to the long term, since they consider each other critical as a family member.

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